

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

**WP7 Information and
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catalogue and quality
support**

D7.10 Test report for FAIR data catalogue (2nd)

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Abstract

The objective of this report is to summarise further user assessments of the second prototype of the ConcePTION FAIR data catalogue (see Deliverable 7.6 for description). The second prototype focuses on presentation of meta-data descriptions of population-based healthcare and surveillance data sources. It also captures details of tools and documentation used to allow data harmonisation across these data sources. Furthermore, it makes use of a user interface enhanced after discussions with users.

Key themes for improvement included introducing definitions around some of the key catalogue sections, additional filtering functionality and installation of a change and authorization log for Data Access Partners (DAPs) updating meta-data.

Introduction

The objective of the ConcePTION data catalogue is to allow researchers to identify relevant Data Access Partners (DAPs) and data sources for the conduct of studies to generate evidence on the safety of medicines used in pregnancy within the ConcePTION network. It also aims to enable ConcePTION partners to manage and transparently share meta-data on individual data items and their conversion to common elements (Common Data Model (CDM), or harmonization, as appropriate) as used in ConcePTION studies as part of federated study analyses. These elements will be delivered according to FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable principles.

The catalogue consists of two main areas hosting different data types and fulfilling different needs:

1. Meta-data describing the DAP Organisation (Institution), the data source(s) the DAP has access to, the data banks within the data source and the individual data items contained within those databanks. These concepts are described in Thurin *et al.* Briefly, the DAP organization may directly control or have access to many data sources. A data source is a collection of data banks which themselves are a collection of structured healthcare data where records are prompted whenever a specific event or healthcare interaction (e.g. diagnosis, medication dispensing, birth, death) occurs for persons in a specific population. Data banks contain data items representing the details of the health record and interaction. Population-based healthcare or surveillance data are captured in a separate section from pregnancy report data sources. As described in **Deliverable 7.6**, meta-data captured in the initial catalogue prototype were based on a specially designed survey/questionnaire tool. Researchers will be able to query the meta-data.
2. For ConcePTION studies based on population-based healthcare or surveillance data sources, data are harmonised in a two-step process; first syntactically against the ConcePTION CDM and then on a study-by-study basis into a semantically harmonised set of study specific variables. A second part of the catalogue will house the data dictionaries of the original data, the Extract, Transform and Load (ETL) process and scripts for transformation into the CDM, and the study-based decisions for semantic harmonisation.

The second catalogue prototype described in Deliverable 7.7 focused on section 1) and 2) of the catalogue capturing meta-data on population-based healthcare and surveillance data sources. These sections were developed and populated with data from several population-based healthcare DAPs. This report describes the user test of that Catalogue section for ConcePTION, built using MOLGENIS tools and software. For the purposes of this report, the users are key stakeholders within the project representing both DAPs who have to upload and view their meta-data and ConcePTION investigators querying the catalogue meta-data.

Methods

A two-step user testing approach was taken. The first step comprised one-to-one online video

interviews with four key stakeholders in the ConcePTION project:

- Romin Pajouheshnia, UU, WP lead within collaborating Minerva project
- Rosa Gini, ARS Toscana, WP7 public partner co-lead
- Marianne Cunningham, WP7 industry lead
- Nicolas Thurin, ConcePTION third party DAP at University of Bordeaux and lead author of manuscript on ConcePTION CDM

The catalogue was displayed on screen for the interviewee and the main functionalities available to DAPs and investigators were demonstrated, including (but not limited to):

- Institutions
 - Search for institutions within the total list
 - Display / edit an individual institution
 - Scroll through the available rich metadata which can be stored per institution
- Data sources
 - Search for data sources within the total list
 - Display / edit an individual data source
 - Scroll through the available rich metadata which can be stored per data source
- Data banks
 - Search for data banks within the total list
 - Display / edit an individual data bank
 - Scroll through the available rich metadata which can be stored per data bank
- Display the connections between institutions, data sources and data banks, such as in the DAP relationship
- Display a CDM and its accompanying tables and variables

The interview was unstructured allowing the interviewee ample time to ask questions and control the direction of the demonstration as required. The interviewer noted all the comments made by the interviewees.

The results of the one-to-one interviews were used to design an online survey that was then circulated to 50 individuals from 23 institutions within the ConcePTION project that represented population-based healthcare and surveillance data DAPs, members of the demonstration project teams within WP1 (investigators within population-based healthcare pharmacoepidemiology studies) and members of WP7 that had been involved in supporting the data characterization task, DAP interviews and upload of DAP meta-data to the catalogue (editors of the catalogue). Individuals could fulfil multiple roles within the project. The survey used a mix of 5-point rating scales and free text to elicit feedback on usability. A copy of survey can be found in **Appendix 1**. Potential survey participants were sent up to two reminders to complete the online survey. Results were then extracted into an excel spreadsheet and descriptively analysed.

Results

One-to-one interviews

The feedback received during the one-to-one interviews was collected and grouped into thematic categories which are listed below. Some feedback received, relating to specific informational meta-data corrections, was noted and acted on, but this feedback is not listed below.

The key themes that emerged were:

Feedback on the data model and expected use of the catalogue by DAPs

It became clear that the innovative data model developed within the ConcePTION project (i.e. structuring meta-data as institutions, data sources and data banks) will require some additional explanation and context for catalogue users. Some specific feedback points are listed below:

- “WP1 users (within the planned ConcePTION demonstration projects) might need a higher level of comfort in understanding of and use of the data banks, requiring more explanation and/or context”
- “The data bank concept is complicated. There can be several data banks in one group but without having them clearly defined.”
- “We need more explanation of the links and relationships between the different blocks on the homepage. Introduction page with a glossary and a schematic?”
- “It might be more intuitive to search starting from a data source rather than from a data bank.”
- “It would be good to see how data banks compose a data source. List of data banks in the data source and list of tables in the data bank.”
- The relationships between institutions and other resources (data banks, data sources, networks) need to be defined more clearly:
 - “ProviderOf [in an institution] is a mix of various different resources, but this is only clear when you go into an individual institution in Edit mode (“Query that lists all resources (data sources, data banks, cohorts, networks) that this institution is access provider of”). Until then it’s not clear why there are different types of data in this list, and what ‘provider of’ actually means.”
 - “We need to define the link between a DAP and a data source e.g. University of Bordeaux as a DAP is the user of the French National Data (SNDS) so does that count as its ‘institute’?”
 - “‘PartnerIn’ is also a mix of different resources. Surely institutes can only be a partner in a network? Are they ‘participants’ in a study (or do we need another word for this?)?”
 - “What’s the difference between the relationship data source<->institution and data source<-> DAP? You can add an institution in two different places within a data source and this is unclear.”
 - “We need clearer definitions of why particular resources belong to ‘providerOf’ and ‘partnerIn’”

Feedback on population of the catalogue (now and in the future)

The DAPs currently have access to what is termed a ‘staging area’ to submit and review the metadata they hold in the catalogue, before it is submitted into the catalogue and shared with all users of the catalogue. Review of their own rich metadata (metadata *about* an institution / data source / data bank/data items), however, currently occurs in the central system in which edits to the variables in the staging areas are transferred. This prompted the following feedback:

- “Who is entitled to change what?”
- “Do we keep a change log?”
- “What about sustainability in terms of input of data? Should DAPs be able to do this themselves?”

It became clear that not all meaning derived from the catalogue can be determined by the software alone and that DAPs also have a role in ensuring that meaningful data is entered:

- “Data banks need more meaningful names besides their acronyms.”

Feedback on the user interface

Interviewees not directly involved in the design and construction of the catalogue were perfectly positioned to give their initial reaction to the catalogue and its user interface. Other interviewees could give more specific feedback with their own use cases in mind. Feedback received on the user interface was the following:

- “Setup looks good, structure looks nice.”
- In the lists of resources such as Institutions / Data sources / Data banks, there should be standard columns in the initial presentation of a list. For example, “Add the name ‘ProviderOf’ as a standard column in the list of Institutions”, “Have the data source as a standard column in the data bank list” or “I would like standard columns in the list of tables in a data bank”.
- “Sorting of lists needs to be made possible.”

In line with the need described above for more explanation and context for users:

- “Column headings could do with more explanation and more intuitive names – eg ‘ProviderOf’, what is this?”
- “Short descriptions would be useful as an extra column when identifying eg data banks in the list”

The use of the name ‘pid’ (‘Persistent Identifier’) as the key identifier for an institution / data source / data bank was called into question since the field currently does not refer to an externally validated pid. The vision for the catalogue is that it will in the future use externally validated pids, and this will be addressed in due course.

Online survey

Eleven institutions, out of 23 approached, completed the online survey. This represented 9 public institutions (primarily academic) and 2 industry institutions. The respondents represented 9 DAPs, 7 investigators from WP1 and 2 investigators from WP7 (data characterization study only). There was often overlap in the roles. Respondents completed the parts of the survey relevant to their role and the quantitative aspects are summarized below.

Use of the catalogue to edit content using the edit/pencil tools

This section of the survey was completed by 4 institutions who were all DAPs. Three of the four marked the ease of use as easy or very easy to use. One respondent noted this as very difficult to use as it was not possible to understand how the different catalogue sheets were linked which meant when editing one level of information you can receive error messages because of an inbuilt hierarchy which was not clear. One suggestion for improvement was for greater flexibility in moving between the levels of institution, data source, data bank and data item as currently to edit any item at any level you must approach it by starting at the highest institution level.

[editor’s comment: actually there are other ways to edit but we can conclude that these are not easy enough to find]

Recommendations: implement a shortcut to edit the current page.

Use of catalogue to browse meta-data content

This section of the survey was completed by 9 institutions, 7 of whom were DAPs and 2 who were investigators. There was a spread of ranking of ease of use for browsing (5 found it easy, 2 were neutral and 2 found it difficult). The lower scores were driven by lack of familiarity with the catalogue and filtering function which can return a mix of data banks and data sources when filtering on an institution and therefore provide duplicate or a large amount of information that is hard to navigate.

Overall, there was positive feedback on the organisation of the catalogue content: 5 of 9 institutions marking this as good (with 4 marking it as neutral). The explanations of the different catalogue sections could be improved as 7 of 9 institutions found this difficult or neutral to understand.

The ease of following links within the catalogue was ranked as easy or very easy by 6 out of 8 institutions answering that question. Within the free text feedback there was a recommendation to add a “go-back” function and to improve the explanations around how the different sections of the catalogue link together. This could include an additional definitions page as well as a figure visualising the different levels of meta-data that can be navigated through.

Of the DAPs who responded to the question on whether any meta-data content was missing, 6 of 9 responded there appeared to be some missing information so some additional checks on the uploaded information will be needed. In terms of the catalogue content there was also a request for additional filtering capabilities specifically at the variable level if the user wants to identify data sources with specific data items to answer specific research questions.

Recommendations

- add a “go-back” function
- improve the explanations around how the different sections of the catalogue link together
- add a figure visualising the different levels of meta-data that can be navigated through
- additional checks on uploaded information
- additional filtering capabilities

General recommendations

Nine investigators answered the question about whether they would recommend the catalogue to other investigators for the purposing of identifying datasources for pregnancy research. The distribution of responses was broad: 4 said they were unlikely or very unlikely to recommend it as a tool whereas 3 responded they were likely or very likely to recommend it with 2 neutral responses.

Nine DAPs answered the question about whether they would recommend to fellow DAPs to display their data in the catalogue and 6 of those 9 responded they were likely or very likely to recommend it. The lower scores for this question were driven by comments around difficulties perceived in browsing the catalogue.

Discussion

We thank all interviewees and reviewers for their time and great input.

Some key themes emerged from the intensive one-to-one interviews that were consistent with the online survey capturing DAPs and investigators within the ConcePTION project. There was a clear call for some additional explanations to guide the reader around some key definitions employed within the structure of the catalogue, namely institutions, datasources, databanks and data items; as well as a need to demonstrate the links between these levels/parts of the catalogue. Continued communication around these concepts, through publication, webinars, utility within demonstration projects, could further enhance familiarity to enhance catalogue usability.

In general, the feedback on the usability of the catalogue in terms of browsing and finding information of interest was positive, though there were some suggestions for improvement that were highlighted including “go back” functions to improve ease of moving between sections of the catalogue and some additional filtering functionality.

Some final checks around the uploaded meta-data to ensure completeness of data and consistency of information across different catalogue sections should be built into the finalization of the catalogue.

A future activity, identified through the one-to-one interviews for the catalogue could be the installation of a change log and development of the necessary authorisations restricting changes to a DAPs own

meta-data, either by making use of a staging area per DAP for both variables and rich metadata, or by introducing row-level security in the central system. In collaboration with other projects, the MOLGENIS team is considering redesign of data submission system to make it easier to create and understand the role of the staging areas, which are in fact just 'draft submissions' of additions/changes into the catalogue, with an optional review step.

Conclusion

In summary, we have received very useful feedback from enthusiastic and engaged users, enabling us further to improve the catalogue, and which provide input for future requests for funding as multiple EU projects are now contributing to the catalogue platform, see for example <http://data-catalogue.molgeniscloud.org> (which uses the same underlying models but then specialized into cohorts). Ultimately our goal would be to create a community catalogue as a SaaS (Software as a Service), in which feedback from the users can continue to play a prominent role in development.

References

Thurin NH, Pajouheshnia R, Roberto G, Dodd C, Hyeraci G, Bartolini C, *et al.* From Inception to ConcePTION: Genesis of a Network to Support Better Monitoring and Communication of Medication Safety During Pregnancy and Breastfeeding. *Clinical Pharmacology and Therapeutics*. 2021; doi:10.1002/cpt.2476

Appendix 1

Questions asked in the online survey:

Name

Organisation

1. Role in the project (multiple answers are possible)

- DAP

- Investigator in WP7 study

- Investigator in WP1 study

- Other

2. Did you use the catalogue to edit content using the edit/pencil tool? (Yes/No)

3a. How easy did you find the edit functionality to use? (1: very difficult, 5: very easy)

3b. Can you explain your answer to question 3a?

4. Did you use the catalogue to browse content? (Yes/No)

4a. How easy did you find the browsing functionality to use? (1: very difficult, 5: very easy)

4b. Can you explain your answer to question 4a?

4c. In terms of content: was there any important content missing? (Yes/No)

4d. If yes, what?

4e. Was the catalogue content well organised? (1: not well organised, 5: very well organised)

4f. Did you find the different sections (Institutions, Datasources, Databanks) of the Catalogue easy to understand? (1: very difficult to understand, 5: very easy to understand)

4g. Did you find it easy to follow the links within the Catalogue? (1: very difficult to follow, 5: very easy to follow)

4h. Can you explain your answers to the three questions directly above about navigation?

5. Did you use the catalogue to upload content using a spreadsheet template? (Yes/No)

5a. How intuitive did you find the upload functionality? (1: not intuitive at all, 5: very intuitive)

5b. Can you explain your answer to question 5a?

6. For investigators: would you recommend to fellow researchers to identify relevant datasources using this catalogue? (Please leave this answer blank if it doesn't apply to you.) (1: not at all, 5: yes, absolutely)

7. For DAPs: would you recommend to fellow DAPs to display the contents of their datasources using this catalogue? (Please leave this answer blank if it doesn't apply to you.) (1: not at all, 5: yes, absolutely)

8. Please explain why you would or wouldn't recommend the catalogue to others.